

Nitration of 2-Oxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

BY P. C. MITTER AND SUDHIR CHANDRA PAL.

By the nitration of 1-oxy-3-methylanthraquinone, Eder and Manoukian (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, 9, 54) obtained 1-oxy-3-methyl-4-nitro-, 1-oxy-3-methyl-2'-nitro- and 1-oxy-3-methyl-2:4-dinitroanthraquinone. We investigated the nitration of 2-oxy-3-methylanthraquinone in the hope of obtaining, among others, 2-oxy-3-methyl-4-nitroanthraquinone, which could be used as a convenient starting point for the synthesis of rubiadin-1-methyl ether, a substance which is present in *Morinda longiflora* (Barrowliff and Tutin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1909), but which has not been hitherto synthesised.

The nitration of 2-oxy-3-methylanthraquinone under the conditions employed by Eder and Manoukian (*loc. cit.*) gave however only a mononitro-derivative, which on methylation gave a product identical with the nitration product of 2-methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone. The nitro-compounds can be reduced by aqueous sodium sulphide solution to the corresponding amino-compounds. On treating with potassium methoxide, the nitro-methoxymethylanthraquinone gives a dimethoxy-methylanthraquinone, which gives 3-methylalizarin on de-methylation, indicating thereby that the nitro-group had entered the position 1. On oxidation with manganese dioxide and sulphuric acid, 3-methylalizarin gives 3-methylpurpurin (Mitter and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 688) which on reduction with stannous chloride in alkaline solution gives rubiadin.

Nitration of 3-methylalizarin-dimethyl ether gives a mononitro-derivative, probably the 4-nitro-compound. Attempts at replacement of the nitro-group by methoxyl have not been so far successful.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Nitro-2-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

Two g. of 2-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (Mitter and Sen, *loc. cit.*, p. 636) were dissolved in pure concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c. c.) and finely powdered potassium nitrate (2 g.) was added in small quantities. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath for five hours and left overnight. It was then poured into water, filtered, washed with hot water, and crystallised from a large volume of glacial acetic acid in prisms, m. p. 267° (yield, 1.5 g.). (Found: N, 4.97. $C_{15}H_9O_5N$ requires N, 4.94 per cent.).

1-Nitro-2-methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

2-Methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone (2 g.) was nitrated as in the previous case, and the product crystallised from acetic acid in plates, m. p. 206° (yield 1.5 g.). (Found: N, 4.92. $C_{16}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 4.71 per cent.). The same substance is also obtained by the direct methylation of 1-nitro-2-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

1-Amino-2-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

1-Nitro-2-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (2 g.) was dissolved in 100 c. c. of 5 % sodium sulphide solution and boiled for one hour under reflux. The deep violet solution was filtered on cooling, and the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a red precipitate came down. It was washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles, m. p. 215°-216° (yield, 1 g.) (Found: N, 5.04. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 5.53 per cent.).

1-Amino-2-methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

1-Nitro-2-methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone (2 g.) was reduced with 5 % sodium sulphide as in the previous case, the yellow nitro-compound being converted into red mass during the operation. It was filtered, washed with hot water and crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m. p. 195° (yield, 1 g.). (Found: N, 5.49. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.26 per cent.).

1:2-Dimethoxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

1-Nitro-2-methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone (4 g.) was suspended in 60 c. c. of absolute methyl alcohol and 80 c. c. of potassium methyrate solution (5%) added. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for twelve hours. On pouring into water, a brown precipitate was obtained which was filtered, washed and crystallised from dilute acetic acid in prisms, m. p. 127° (yield, 2.5 g.). (Found: C, 71.96; H, 5.04. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 4.97 per cent.).

3-Methylalizarin.—1:2-Dimethoxy-6-methylanthraquinone (2 g.) was mixed with finely powdered aluminium chloride (2 g.) and heated to 200° in course of one hour, and kept at that temperature for half an hour. When cooled, the reaction mixture was treated with water, boiled with a few c. c. of hydrochloric acid, filtered and the residue dissolved in one per cent. solution of potassium hydroxide. It was filtered and the filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid when yellow flakes appeared. Crystallised from benzene, it was obtained in the form of needles, m. p. 245°.

Diacetyl Derivative of 3-Methylalizarin.

It was prepared in the usual way with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 162°.

The melting point of this compound, given by Mitter and Sen (*loc. cit.*, p. 681) as 262°, is evidently due to manuscript error. (Found: C, 67·84; H, 3·94. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67·46; H, 4·14 per cent.).

3-Methylpurpurin.

Crystallised 3-methylalizarin (2 g.) was oxidized according to the method of Mitter and Sen (*loc. cit.*) and crystallised from benzene in needles, m. p. 231° (yield, 1 g.).

Triacetyl Derivative of 3-Methylpurpurin.

The acetyl derivative was prepared in the usual way and crystallised in needles from alcohol, m.p. 213°. (Found: C, 63·74; H, 4·2. $C_{21}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 63·63; H, 4·04 per cent.).

Rubiadin.—3-Methylpurpurin (1 g.) was dissolved in ten per cent. caustic soda solution, heated to boiling and stannous chloride was added little by little until the original red colour of the solution changed to yellow, care being taken that the stannous salt remains in solution. After cooling, it was precipitated with hydrochloric acid, filtered and the precipitate digested with hydrochloric acid, filtered, washed and dissolved in baryta water, the filtrate from this solution is treated with hydrochloric acid when a yellow mass is obtained, which is crystallised from benzene. The substance has all the properties of rubiadin. It melts at 290°, and its acetyl derivative melts at 225°.

1:2-Dimethoxy-3-methyl-4 (?)-nitroanthraquinone.

1:2-Dimethoxy-3-methylanthraquinone (2 g.) was nitrated with potassium nitrate and sulphuric acid in the usual way and the product recrystallised from acetic acid, in needles, m. p. 248° (yield, 1 g.). (Found: N, 4·59. $C_{17}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 4·3 per cent.).